

IAVCEI 2023 abstract, 30-Jan-3 Feb 2023, Rotorua, NZ

A Brief History of Submarine Volcano Studies with the ALVIN Submersible

Ken Rubin, SOEST, Univ. of Hawaii at Manoa

This presentation will review seminal contributions to submarine volcano science by Human Occupied Vehicle DSV ALVIN since its launch in the mid-1960s. The submersible vehicle has been used for in situ observations over a variety of depths in the deep ocean to enable geological mapping, volcanic stratigraphy and eruption frequency, volcanic deposit facies characterization, lava and pyroclast sampling, geothermal field characterization, and submarine volcano-hosted ecosystem studies in each of its operating decades, which continue through to the present. Drawing on the literature and my own experiences using the vehicle in the current and each of the last three decades, I will highlight some of the notable volcano studies that greatly refined our understanding of lava flow emplacement conditions and history in submarine settings, including at well-known sites on the northern and southern East Pacific Rise, Mid-Atlantic Ridge, Juan de Fuca Ridge, the Galapagos Spreading Center, Loihi (now known as Kamaehuakanaloa), and the Marianas Back Arc. I will also discuss technical capabilities of the submersible and changes over time that have facilitated this research. Results discussed will include recent dives I and others did at up to 6 km depth in the Mid Cayman Rise and Puerto Rico trench, as part of the ALVIN Science Verification Expedition (SVE), which was conducted in July-Aug 2022. This expedition was funded by the US National Science Foundation to evaluate the capabilities and usability of the ALVIN submersible, operated by Woods Hole Oceanographic Institution, after a major rebuild for operations at substantially deeper depth than before (6.5 km vs 4.5 km).